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Pusa 1121: a rice line with exceptionally high cooked kernel elongation and basmati quality

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Among the basmati rice varieties, Basmati 370 and Type 3 have been the most popular in trade circles. In most basmati improvement programs, Basmati 370 was widely used as a parent until the mid-1970s. A local collection from the Karnal region in Haryana State, India, possessing similar cooking quality characteristics but with a longer brown and milled rice kernel length compared with Basmati 370 and Type 3 was selected by IARI scientists and named as Karnal Local as it was collected. Subsequently, variety Taraori Basmati, with similar grain characteristics and cooking quality traits, was released for commercial cultivation. Because of its longer grain, it fetched a higher price in the domestic and international market and slowly started replacing Basmati 370. Later, research focused on developing semidwarf, high-yielding, photoperiod- and temperature-insensitive rice varieties possessing typical basmati quality with greater cooked kernel elongation. This resulted in the development and release of Pusa Basmati 1 in 1989. The popularity of Pusa Basmati 1 in the domestic and international markets provided an impetus for increasing the brown rice length and linear cooked kernel elongation further. By selective intermating of the two elongating advanced breeding sister lines of Pusa Basmati 1, a new breeding line—Pusa 1121—has been developed. We report here the development of Pusa 1121 and

its grain, cooking, and eating characteristics.

During kharif 1992, a large number of single plant selections were made from an F_2 population of a cross (Pusa 614-1-2/Pusa 614-2-4-3) involving two sister lines. During grain and cooking quality evaluation, one of the selections showed exceptionally high linear cooked kernel elongation apart from longer milled kernel length. In subsequent generations, it showed variation in brown rice grain dimension, breadth and texture of cooked rice, and bursting during cooking but remained stable for aroma, linear kernel elongation, and alkali spreading value. After several generations of selection, it has now attained uniform morphological and grain, cooking, and eating quality characteristics.

In the lineage of Pusa 1121, both Basmati 370 and Type 3 are involved. The genes for linear kernel elongation in these two sister lines, Pusa 614-1-2 and Pusa 614-2-4-3, have obviously come from Basmati 370 and Type 3. These genes seem to be different and dispersed in the sister lines. The accumulation of these dispersed genes in Pusa 1121 resulting from selective intermating of sister lines has contributed to increased linear cooked kernel elongation. The involvement of many independent loci in the genetic control of cooked kernel elongation is also evident from the quantitative inheritance (Sood et al 1983) and linkage analysis (Ahn

et al 1993, Ram et al 1998). The gene for longer brown rice length seems to have come from 1B25, which has significantly longer brown rice than the other lines involved in the lineage of Pusa 1121.

Basmati 370, Taraori Basmati, and Pusa Basmati 1 have an average milled rice kernel length of 6.89, 7.15, and 7.30 mm, with elongation ratios of 1.94, 1.90, and 2.02, respectively (see table). In contrast, Pusa 1121 has a milled rice kernel length of 8 mm and elongation ratio of 2.7 during cooking (see figure), without much horizontal swelling. Because of its higher linear cooked kernel elongation ratio, Pusa 1121 makes a better parental material for generating mapping populations to identify and locate genes for linear kernel elongation.

References

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Agronomic and quality characteristics of Pusa 1121 rice.

Feature	Basmati 370	Taraori Basmati	Pusa Basmati I	Pusa 1121
<i>Agronomic</i>				
Plant height (cm)	160–175	160–175	95–110	110–120
Total duration (d)	145–150	155–160	130–135	140–145
Average yield (t ha ⁻¹)	3.0	2.5	5.5	4.0
<i>Kernel characteristics</i>				
Milled rice length (mm)	6.89	7.15	7.30	8.00
Milled rice breadth (mm)	1.85	1.78	1.70	1.90
L-B ratio	3.72	4.13	4.29	4.74
<i>Milling characters</i>				
Hulling (%)	78.0	78.8	77.0	75.0
Milling (%)	72.5	69.0	67.0	70.5
Head rice recovery (%)	53.0	49.9	48.5	54.5
Chalky grain (%)	20.0	18.0	30.0	13.0
<i>Cooking characteristics</i>				
Alkali spreading value	4 or 5	4 or 5	7	7
Amylose (%)	24	22	27	26
Kernel length after cooking (mm)	13.40	14.00	14.75	21.50
Kernel breadth after cooking (mm)	2.40	2.40	2.25	2.45
Kernel elongation ratio	1.94	1.90	2.02	2.70
Aroma	Strong	Strong	Mild	Strong
Rating on cooking	Very good	Very good	Very good	Excellent

Cooked rice kernels of Pusa 1121 (a), Taraori Basmati (b), and Pusa Basmati I (c).

Magat, a wetland semidwarf hybrid rice for high-yielding production on irrigated dryland

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The looming water crisis requires that more rice be produced with less water. To achieve this goal, the development of high-yielding upland rice, which requires no soil flooding, can be explored. We evaluated rice inbreds and hybrids for high yield under fully fertilized and irrigated upland growing conditions, that is, on aerobic soil irrigated to maintain soil water at about field capacity. In three trials, we tested Magat (IR64616H), a lowland semidwarf hybrid, and Apo, an improved upland indica, along with other lowland or upland entries. In a fourth trial, Magat was compared with other lowland hybrids. Trial 1 (Table 1) on an acid [pH (KCl)

3.7] upland soil (Ultisol) consisted of four varieties and three plant populations arranged in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with four replications in plots of 34 m². This soil was limed with 3 t ha⁻¹ of CaCO₃. In trial 2 (Table 2) on a less acid [pH (KCl) 5.4] Alfisol, Magat and Apo were grown in fumigated and nonfumigated soil in a split-plot design in 52-m² plots. Trial 3 included five upland varieties in an RCBD with four replications in 20-m² plots (Table 3). Ten lowland hybrids and two upland varieties replicated thrice in an RCBD in 6-m² plots made up trial 4 (Table 3). Both trials 3 and 4 were on the same soil as trial 2. In all trials, N was

supplied in frequent splits to keep the plants green.

Magat yielded the highest in all but trial 2, with a maximum yield of 8.2 t ha⁻¹ measured in trial 1 (Tables 1, 2, and 3). In trial 2, Magat's 5.7 t ha⁻¹ yield on fumigated soil was on a par with Apo's 6.2 t ha⁻¹. Across the three trials where Magat and Apo were compared, Magat outyielded Apo, a high-yielding upland rice (George et al 2001), by 1 t ha⁻¹. Magat also outyielded nine other lowland hybrids in trial 4. Magat's high yield was largely due to its ability to retain a high harvest index relative to other varieties with high biomass yields, as many other varieties are